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Abstract

The working population of India was hardly hit by the COVID pandemic and the livelihood crisis arising from the same. Mismanagement in the lockdown process leads to confusion and overcrowding. Lockdown and curbing economic activity leads to loss of jobs, low farm prices, people didn't have money to purchase the things and as a result overall demand decreased which affected the factory output and services sector. This all result in rise of unemployment rate in rural and urban areas. The main sufferers of COVID-19 pandemic are workers of informal or unorganized sector as mostly started losing jobs due to closure of factories. As a consequence, lakhs of people marched towards their native villages hundreds of miles away without any transport facility. Worldwide the young persons have found themselves out of the labour market and adverse effect of COVID pandemic is seen lasting for many years to come. An analysis of employment status during COVID times highlights the fact that restrictions on travel, increasing lockdowns and curbing economic activities in different states served to endanger the economic sectors and system and to a great extent increases the unemployment rate. An unexpected and sudden rise of migration of workers further made the situation vulnerable and it leads to heavy burden on state government's machinery. The paper highlights the employment status during COVID times. The paper presents constructive suggestions of reducing the unemployment rate in India. The paper concludes with the fact that in the year to come, there may be some hope of increasing the economic activity as third peak of corona virus is over.

Key words: Unemployment rate, pandemic, self employment, workers, COVID-19

INTRODUCTION

The first case of COVID case in India was recorded in January 2020. Since then, the number of confirmed cases in mid February 2022 increased to more than 4 crores 28 lakhs with 5 Lakhs 12 thousand deaths. The Central Government announced a nationwide lockdown on March 24, 2020 aimed to slow down the spread of the virus. The threat posed by the Coronavirus new variant Omicron had compelled various Indian states to impose fresh restrictions and curbs on economic activity and as a result, affects the consumption rate leading to a rise in the unemployment rate. Our country is facing economic turmoil due to the COVID pandemic leading many workers out of work. An important factor in the Indian economy which continues to be of primary concern is the lack of jobs with levels of employment remains worse when we compare with pre-covid times. Also, the participation rate of the labour force is worsening than in pre-covid times. In India, urban unemployment is the biggest worry in today's times. In the year 2020 the employment rate rose to its highest level since 1991 due to the Covid pandemic. The economy comes to a standstill due to the pandemic. Our country had seen the toughest lockdown in its history started in March 2020 with strict restrictions on economic activities and mobility. The unemployment rate rose to 7.1 % in the year 2020 as compared to 5.2 % in the year 2019. There is no doubt that COVID 19 pandemic had negatively impacted the employment status since early 2020. We have seen different scenarios such as lockdown in factories, a big line of labourers who lost their jobs with hungry children, wives and other family members who were carrying loads on their heads moving towards their villages. Due to lockdown, they were not able to get any transport. But these helpless migrants took to the road for unknown places or native places. The unemployment rate is rising which leads to the loss of jobs during this COVID times. The rate of unemployment stands to 12.4 % consisting of 15.1 % in urban

areas and 11.2 % in rural areas in June 2021. We had seen that the manufacturing sector including engineering has severely affected by the lockdown during the second wave of COVID.

The rate of unemployment refers to the percentage of workers who are unemployed in the labour force. Persons who are employed as well as persons who are unemployed but looking for work are included in the labour force. Till now, the first wave and second wave have hurt all sectors of Indian economy but mostly self employed people and informal workers are most hurted.

Table 1: Unemployment Rate

	November 2021	December 2021	December 2020
Unemployment rate (%)	7.0	7.9	9.1

Source: Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)

Table 2: Urban and Rural Unemployment Rate

	Urban Unemployment Rate (%)	Rural Unemployment Rate (%)
December 2021	9.3	7.3
November 2021	8.2	6.4

Source: Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)

From the above tables, it is clear that there is a surge in unemployment rate in December 2021 and this signals the sustained risks to the economy of India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study has been undertaken to analyze the impact of lockdown in COVID times on the employment rate. The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand, it is applicable to the whole of India. However, the opinion of businessmen and other stakeholders in the Moradabad district of Uttar Pradesh and Jaipur, Rajasthan has been taken about the loss of jobs in various sectors of the economy. Their views have been incorporated into this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on reducing the employment rate in these tough times.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study entitled “An Analysis of Employment Status During COVID Times” are mentioned herein below:

- To highlight the status of employment during the COVID period.
- To analyze the impact of lockdown on the employment rate.
- To present suggestions to mitigate the loss of employment in COVID times.

ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYMENT STATUS DURING COVID TIMES

The biggest loss is suffered by salaried persons as opposed to the common belief that salaried persons are safe in terms of employment and earnings.

Table 3: Loss of Jobs

	2019-20		2020-21		Loss of Jobs (Millions)	Loss of jobs in Urban areas (%)
	2019-20 (Millions)	Percentage of urban salaried jobs out of all salaried jobs in the country (%)	End of March 21 (Millions)	Percentage of rural salaried jobs out of all salaried jobs in the country (%)		
Salaried Jobs	85.9	58	76.2	42	9.8	38 %

Source: Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)

The persons who have lost their jobs migrated to farming. The above data clearly indicates that States and Central Governments should take initiatives for the creation and retention of secured jobs.

An analysis of employment status during COVID times and the impact of the pandemic on employment rate are done herein below:

1. Loss of urban jobs resulted in the migration of workers from urban areas to villages and this again increased the burden on agricultural farms in villages. The migration is happening from the states of Delhi, Maharashtra and Gujarat. The workers are returning to states of Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and a few eastern states as the majority of the workers belong to these states.
2. As per the report of the Standing Committee on Labour, 2021, in India around 90 percent of workers belong to the informal sector which includes vendors working on street, workers involved in construction work, workers who are termed as migrants and workers who are termed as contract labourers. In the unorganized sector, there is a lack of relationship between employee and employer as well as there is a seasonality of employment, all these workers were adversely affected by the COVID pandemic.
3. Approximately, 50 % of salaried workers in the formal sector transformed to the informal sector either as self-employed or casual workers or informal salaried workers between the period of the second half of 2019 and the end of the year 2020. This leads to a decline in the income level of all these workers.
4. Before COVID 19, the unemployment rate of females is generally higher than the unemployment rate of male persons in India. Since the beginning of the COVID 19 pandemic, the gap between female and male unemployment rates seems to have widened.

Table 4: Unemployment Rate in Pre-COVID and COVID Times

Pre-COVID 19		COVID 19 Times	
Unemployment Rate		Unemployment Rate	
Female	Male	Female	Male
9.8 %	7.3 %	13.1 %	9.5 %

Source: Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE)

5. Many economists believe that few of the job losses will be long term in nature.
6. During different waves of virus in the country, it is obvious that there may be some mismanagement in every field which leads to make the situation of employment more vulnerable.
7. Lower income in COVID times leads to lower demand for the products as well as low investment and income. This will result in loss of livelihoods.
8. Many industries especially hospitality and entertainment will remain adversely impacted by the pandemic. Now things are improving, so the majority of the organizations are better prepared to handle the adverse situations. Some companies are hiring in rural areas, especially in sectors like microfinance, retail assets, housing, etc. In urban areas, hiring is going on in sectors like FMCG, e-commerce and telecom.
9. In recent times, the manufacturing sector had experienced a brake because exports, as well as demand within the country, declined, also there was a credit crunch. Many organizations had stopped production which includes paper, textiles, bicycles, rice milling, tea factories, etc. which results in loss of employment to a great extent.
10. During lockdown there were restrictions on movement which had a direct adverse impact on business and trade particularly retail trade. The majority of the workers in this category are self-employed who had a tough time in this period.
11. Casual workers in urban areas who are mainly employed in the construction and manufacturing sector suddenly lose their jobs along with their accommodation as the majority live in the work premises or in dwellings provided or arranged by their contractors. These types of workers have no choice but to migrate to their native villages. Unlike workers in rural areas, the workers in urban areas were not covered under various poverty alleviation programmes. Though various financial packages were announced by Central Government, but the majority of workers were left behind.

12. The financial assistance from the government side or from the employer side was received to meagre workers. In the absence of financial assistance and job protection worklessness resulted in a reduction in earnings.
13. Unlike workers in the formal sector, informal workers did not have the means to work from home. As a result, they were not paid for maximum days and remained idle for many months.
14. Unlike men, women are marginally to be in irregular employment. Therefore, the pandemic impacted them most leading to more vulnerability in their employment as a result forcing them to be in care work responsibilities.

SUGGESTIONS

In view of the pandemic scenario, the central and all state governments should take steps in the following areas:

- 1) In India, tackling unemployment is the most important concern for the government right now. This is a crisis that is termed humanitarian so the government in such an emergency should be the employer of the last resort.
- 2) Increase the opportunities for entrepreneurial activities.
- 3) Training should be provided to women in new technologies.
- 4) Providing financial support to women for self-employment.
- 5) Reach of job scheme MNREGA should be expanded in rural areas.
- 6) Increase of procurement from women-led organizations by the government.
- 7) Payroll support to MSMEs so that workers should not be retrenched during tough times.
- 8) Promote vocational training. However, our New Education Policy has made a provision for vocational courses at the graduate level.
- 9) Decentralization of industrial activity should be encouraged so that employment generation should be done in all areas.
- 10) Social security measures should be strengthened.
- 11) Investment should be made in industrial clusters.
- 12) Policy should be framed which creates jobs for all.
- 13) Investment should be made in traditional manufacturing sectors.
- 14) Improvement in job prospects along with labour productivity
- 15) The commitment in terms of national policy is needed to avoid the current income losses, also avoiding the movement of workers into urban poverty and prevent the risk of long term unemployment.
- 16) Village and cottage industries which are included in the ambit of small scale industry are found to be the best remedy for increasing unemployment of youth. Also, self-employment is considered the best option to tackle unemployment.
- 17) The road to recovery after COVID lockdown lies in re-skilling of workers especially in sectors like hospitality, healthcare and education because these sectors engage large number of women which have been badly hit by the pandemic.

CONCLUSION

According to the Periodic Labour Force Survey, though the rate of unemployment and participation rate of the labour force have improved since COVID times but still not recovered to the levels of pre-COVID times. People are now coming back to their jobs but in more insecure and uncertain ways. Due to more than two years old COVID, the Indian economy is suffering a lot on various grounds. Strategies like lockdown and other restrictions helped to reduce the coronavirus but these strategies have created adverse effects on the Indian economy.

To conclude, we can say that there are expectations among the masses that India has crossed the third wave of pandemic even then the normalcy in the labour markets may not resume very soon. In the coming year 2022-23, there may be some hope of increasing the economic activity as the third peak of coronavirus is over. This may result in an increasing employment rate due to the opening of

factories and other manufacturing concerns leading to a rise in economic activities. The central government as well as all state governments to give priority to the process of vaccination so that people will not be badly affected by the virus.

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